

Kinematic model of 90° domain boundaries in barium titanate

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A kinematic model of 90° domain boundaries in barium titanate is developed. The model is based on an inhomogeneous two-dimensional shear strain field constrained to exhibit reflection symmetry across an extended boundary region. Model development proceeds by sequential consideration of one and two dimensional homogeneous simple shear, one and two dimensional inhomogeneous shear, and finally constrained two dimensional inhomogeneous shear. Diagrams of the various deformation modes are presented. Electric polarization is mapped onto the domain boundary region, consistent with boundary symmetry. An example similar to experimentally observed lamellar domain arrays is given.

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1. Introduction

The dielectric most often used in multi-layer ceramic capacitors (MLCC)s is the oxide compound barium titanate (BaTiO_3) [Kishi *et al.*, 2003; Pan and Randall, 2010; Hong *et al.*, 2019]. Small, sub-millimeter scale MLCCs are pervasive in microelectronic devices, including cell phones, hand held tablets, and electric vehicles. The electrical and mechanical behavior of BaTiO_3 is critical to MLCC performance, including reliability, and, as with most compounds, electrical and mechanical behavior in BaTiO_3 are coupled through structure. The work here provides a simple analytical description of an important structural feature in BaTiO_3 : the 90° domain boundary, described below. The description is flexible enough to describe a range of microstructural variants, is amenable to experimental verification, and includes explicit information regarding electrical polarization and mechanical strain. Such descriptions are increasingly important as MLCC structures approach the nano scale.

At room temperature, BaTiO_3 forms a tetragonal unit cell with two equivalent, perpendicular, a axes, $a = 0.3991$ nm, and a longer, mutually perpendicular, c axis, $c = 0.4035$ nm, such that the tetragonal distortion from cubic, $(c/a - 1)$, is about 1.1 % [Kwei *et al.*, 1993]. The tetragonal unit cell exterior is defined by Ba^{2+} ions at the cell vertices and O^{2-} ions at the face centers. An interior Ti^{4+} ion is displaced parallel to the c axis from the cell center to generate a polarized unit cell with electric dipole aligned along the c axis. The nano-scale crystal structure of BaTiO_3 at room temperature is ferroelectric, consisting of aligned dipoles and unit cells. The larger micro-scale structure consists of locally-invariant divisions of crystallographic and polarization alignment known as domains [Jona and Shirane, 1993]. Domain formation minimizes the elastostatic and electrostatic energy of an entire microstructure or specimen [Arlt, 1990]. The regions of crystallographic and polarization transition between domains are known as domain boundaries. A particularly important and pervasive domain boundary, responsible for much of the energy minimization in BaTiO_3 structures, separates domains oriented relative to each other by approximately 90° . A recent series of experimental works has measured and mapped the deformation—strain and rotation—and associated stress in multi-domain BaTiO_3 structures formed by 90° domain boundaries [Howell *et al.*, 2014, 2017, 2019, 2020]. The maps were generated by electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) techniques at the nano-scale and provide much of the motivation for the current work.

The major features of a 90° domain boundary in BaTiO_3 are shown in the often presented schematic representation of Fig. 1 (see [Howell, 2019] for lists of previous depictions). The \mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{e}_2 - \mathbf{e}_3 right handed laboratory coordinate system used here and earlier [Howell *et al.*, 2014, 2017, 2019, 2020] is shown, with \mathbf{e}_1 positive right, \mathbf{e}_2 positive into the plane of the diagram, and \mathbf{e}_3 positive up. The long and short axes of the rectangles in Fig. 1 represent unit cell c and a axes,

respectively, the arrows represent the electrical dipole orientations, and the dashed line identifies domain boundary cells. The conventional unit cell notation sets the crystallographic directions [100]-[010]-[001] coincident with \mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{e}_2 - \mathbf{e}_3 , as shown on the left of the diagram. At larger scale, regions of fixed ferroelectric polarization in a BaTiO₃ microstructure are here termed c domains if the constituent dipoles and c axes are substantially aligned parallel to \mathbf{e}_3 and a domains if the dipoles and c axes are substantially aligned parallel to \mathbf{e}_1 . The previous investigations of BaTiO₃ crystals show that these relative orientations are almost exclusively the case, along with alignment of one of the a axes almost parallel to \mathbf{e}_2 ; the angular deviations from these alignments are extremely small, $< 1^\circ$. The geometrical relationship between a unit cell within a c domain and one within an a domain is thus a rotation of approximately 90° about the \mathbf{e}_2 -aligned [010] a axis. The structural sequence represented in Fig. 1, using previous notation [Howell, 2019, 2020], is thus $c^+//a^+$, in which letters represent domain orientations, superscripts represent dipole orientations relative to the appropriate axis, and // represents a domain boundary.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of 90° domain boundary structure in BaTiO₃. The domains either side of the boundary are indicated by the orientations of rectangles representing unit cells and arrows representing electric dipoles. The boundary cells are kite shaped and contain a line of reflection symmetry between the two domains, indicated dashed.

It is noted that the representation of Fig. 1, in which the domains either side of the boundary are related by a rigid rotation, localizes all domain boundary deformation in an inclined row of single cells. The deformation is regarded as twin-like, [Cheng *et al.*, 2006, 2008] in the sense that the *exteriors* of the cells either side of the boundary are related by reflection symmetry across the boundary and reflection plane indicated by the dashed line. This symmetry has the consequences that (i) the exteriors of the inclined row of domain boundary cells are deformed to a kite shape and (ii) the relative cell orientations in the adjacent a and c domains

deviate from 90° by a fixed angle θ_r . Further, charge neutrality at the domain boundary (iii) constrains the *interior* dipoles of the unit cells to maintain a “head-to-tail” orientation. Given these three constraints, the orientation of dipoles in adjacent domains then specifies the relative domain orientation in terms of $\pm\theta_r$ and the relative domain boundary inclination. For example, the selection of c^+ followed by a^+ in Fig. 1 requires the rigid rotation angle to be $90^\circ + \theta_r$ and the domain boundary to incline downward to the right, such that the boundary trace is parallel to $[10\bar{1}]$ in conventional crystallographic notation. Consistent with usual angular sign conventions, clockwise rotation and thus θ_r in Fig. 1 are positive. The “rigid rotation” angle, θ_r , is approximately equal to the tetragonal distortion, which for BaTiO_3 is approximately 10^{-2} , or in angular terms about 10 mrad or 0.63° (details below). For visualization purposes, the tetragonal distortion and consequently θ_r are exaggerated in the diagrams throughout. In Fig. 1 this exaggeration is a factor of 20.

In the most recent EBSD-based investigation of BaTiO_3 [Howell *et al.*, 2020], attention was focused on a predominantly c domain crystal that contained small, isolated a domains. Stress, strain, and rotation maps were generated of the a domains and surrounding regions. In particular, variations of the out of plane rotation relative to the ideal a or c orientation were measured. A major feature of agreement between these observations and the model of Fig. 1 is that the rotations within a domains relative to those within surrounding c domains exhibited maxima of approximately $\theta_r \approx 0.63^\circ$. Similar rotations with maximum magnitudes close to $|\theta_r|$ were also observed in other extensive EBSD studies of BaTiO_3 microstructures, including bundles of domains [Howell, 2017, 2019] and arrays of lamellar domains [Howell, 2014].

A major feature of disagreement between the experimental observations and Fig. 1, however, is that the observed rotation variations were extended, and not abrupt changes as suggested by the model. In addition, all of the observed domain structures, isolated, bundled, and lamellar, exhibited extended strain variations that, although peaking at the BaTiO_3 tetragonal distortion value [Howell, 2014, 2017, 2019, 2020], were consistent with gradual structural changes. Further support for gradual change comes from extensive one dimensional [Cao and Barsch, 1990; Cao and Cross, 1991], two dimensional [Hu and Chen, 1997; Zhang and Battacharya, 2005], and three dimensional [Hu and Chen, 1998; Su and Landis, 2007; Woldman and Landis, 2016] models of multi-domain BaTiO_3 structures that include elastostatic and electrostatic energetic effects. The models are based on the Devonshire extension of the Landau model of phase transitions in dielectrics [Cao and Barsch, 1990] and include contributions from strain, polarization, and their coupling. The outputs are usually focused on electrical effects and show gradual variations in polarization and amplitude orientation at domain boundaries. The associated deformation or strain variations extend over many unit cells, suggesting that energy minimization effects lead to gradual structural changes, consistent with observations.

Alternatively, it is possible that axial convolution or “information depth” effects arising from the electron beam based EBSD measurements could contribute to observed smoothing of actually abrupt transitions. Such effects are expected to extend to depths of about 30 nm to 50 nm in BaTiO₃. Lateral convolution or “beam spreading” effects are expected to be much smaller than this given the approximate 5 nm beam size. Hence convolution effects are anticipated to be small, a few tens of nm, relative to the observed length scales of rotation variation, many hundreds of nm; equivalently, convolution effects are expected to affect only one or two adjoining pixels in maps of near mega-pixel dimensions and not affect observations of gradual changes.

The above considerations make clear that refinement of the BaTiO₃ 90° domain boundary model is required. The refinement should retain the major features of Fig. 1, consistent with the twin-like observations of domain orientation either side of the boundary, but should also result in gradual structural variation at the domain boundary, more consistent with the recent EBSD observations and the energetically-based models. Such a 90° domain boundary model for BaTiO₃ is developed here. The refined model is based on inhomogeneous, or non-affine, two-dimensional shear deformation of material separating two domains related by rigid rotation. The model is kinematic in that only the deformation of the BaTiO₃ unit cells and changes in orientation of polarization across the domain boundary are described, not the causal forces or energetics. However, the model will have as its goal the gradualism that typifies energetic formulations. The model is implemented such that the outputs can be compared directly with experimental observations and analytical predictions (comparisons that are often not easy with the Devonshire-Landau models).

The work here begins with descriptions of domain boundary variants as observed by EBSD measurements. The descriptions make a clear connection between structures observed in the laboratory reference frame and those observed in the boundary frame, greatly reducing analysis requirements. Ensuing model development then starts with three general descriptions of deformation of increasing complexity: (i) homogeneous one-dimensional simple shear; followed by (ii) inhomogeneous one-dimensional simple shear; and then (iii) inhomogeneous two-dimensional shear. These general considerations are followed by development of the specific deformation of inhomogeneous two-dimensional shear constrained to generate reflection symmetry between the initial and final states. In essence, the single boundary cells of Fig. 1 will be replaced by an array of cells, each exhibiting a distinct deformation. Electrical polarization transformations between these boundary cells will be gradual and implemented as a superposed inhomogeneous field coupled to the shear deformation. An example of model application is then considered.

2. Analysis

2.1. Domain Boundary Structures

Figure 2 shows as minimal sets of three cells the eight variants of domain boundaries observed by EBSD in laboratory coordinates and discussed above. The electron beam in EBSD is typically directed along $-\mathbf{e}_3$ and scanning is typically directed along $+\mathbf{e}_1$. EBSD provides both domain orientation and domain sequence. For example, Fig. 2(a) represents Fig. 1, the c^+/a^+ structure. Other examples are that Fig. 2(c) represents c^+/a^- and Fig. 2(h) represents a^-/c^+ . Note that EBSD cannot usually determine the \pm polarizations directly but does determine the detailed orientation of the domains either side of a boundary from which the polarizations and boundary orientation can be inferred. For example, EBSD can distinguish the single boundary structures of Figs. 2(a) from 2(c) and Figs. 2(c) from 2(h). Combinations of 2(a) through 2(h) can describe various multiple domain structures. For example, the sequence Figs. 2(a), 2(e), 2(a), 2(e), 2(a), 2(e), 2(a) describes $c^+/a^+/c^+/a^+/c^+/a^+/c^+$ and the periodic lamellar domains studied previously [Howell, 2014]. The sequence Figs. 2(a) and 2(g) describes $c^+/a^+/c^-$ and the surface structure of an a domain studied as part of a bundle [Howell, 2017, 2019]. The sequence Figs. 2(c) and 2(h) describes $c^+/a^-/c^+$ and the surface structure of a single isolated a domain [Howell, 2020].

Close inspection of Fig. 2 shows that the eight structural variants in laboratory coordinates are in fact identical structures when viewed in the frame of reference of the boundary cell. **Figure 3** shows the same groups of cells as Fig. 2 but with the c cells in each group translated in the \mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{e}_3 plane so as to impinge on the short side of the dotted boundary cell rather than the long side as in Fig. 2. The commonality of the structures is now clear and all eight variations in Fig. 3 can be interchanged using combinations of rotation about \mathbf{e}_2 and reflection in either \mathbf{e}_1 or \mathbf{e}_3 . Alternatively, Figs. 2 and 3 make clear that the kinematic transformation between the cells either side of a 90° boundary in BaTiO_3 can be described by either a rotation of $(90 + \theta_r)$ and translation of the rotated cell or a reflection in the boundary plane and inversion through the center of the reflected cell. The importance of Figs. 2 and 3 is that detailed analysis for only one particular transformation need be developed as analyses for all other transformations can be obtained from symmetry operations. Hence, analysis describing the commonly cited c^+/a^+ structural transformation, Figs. 1, 2(a), and 3(a), will be developed here and other transformations obtained by symmetry. Development of the analysis begins in the following section by consideration of the general shears required.

Figure 2. Schematic diagrams of the eight $c//a$ BaTiO₃ domain boundary variants observed in the e_1 - e_2 - e_3 laboratory frame. Domains are indicated by rectangular unit cells and dipole arrows, boundary cells are kite shaped and include a dashed symmetry line.

Figure 3. Schematic diagrams of the eight $c//a$ BaTiO₃ domain boundary variants from Fig. 2, rendered into the boundary reference frame by cell translation. The c and a cells now have the same relation to the boundary cell and the identical nature of the boundary transformations is clear.

2.2. General Shear Deformation

The initial position of a material point in an undeformed body is here denoted X_i , where $i = (1, 2, 3)$ is in relation to the \mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{e}_2 - \mathbf{e}_3 axes. The final position of the material point in the deformed body is denoted x_i . The material deformation tensor relating the two positions, F_{ij} , is defined by $F_{ij} = \partial x_i / \partial X_j$ [Mase, 1970]. A general linear expression for F_{ij} , expressed in the undeformed coordinates, is

$$F_{ij} = F_{ij}^0 + f_{ij}^{(i)} X_i + f_{ij}^{(j)} X_j, \quad (1)$$

where F_{ij}^0 is the familiar term characterizing homogeneous deformation and $f_{ij}^{(i)}$ and $f_{ij}^{(j)}$ are terms characterizing inhomogeneous deformation. Here, only curvature-free (see Appendix) homogeneous and inhomogeneous shear deformation in the \mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{e}_3 plane is considered such that Eq. (1) is reduced considerably to

$$F_{11}^0 = F_{33}^0 = 1, \quad (2a)$$

$$F_{13} = F_{13}^{(0)} + f_{13}^{(1)} X_1, \quad (2b)$$

and

$$F_{31} = F_{31}^{(0)} + f_{31}^{(3)} X_3, \quad (2c)$$

with all other terms zero. On integration of the F_{ij} terms in Eq. (2), the relation between the deformed and undeformed coordinates, (x_1, x_3) and (X_1, X_3) , respectively, expressed in matrix form is thus

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & F_{13}^{(0)} + f_{13}^{(1)} X_1 \\ F_{31}^{(0)} + f_{31}^{(3)} X_3 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X_1 \\ X_3 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) shows that the transformation may include terms in the product $X_1 X_3$ but does not introduce deformation curvature (quadratic terms in X_1^2 and X_3^2 reflecting deformation curvature are considered in the Appendix).

Figure 4 shows a set of undeformed unit squares as dashed lines in the \mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{e}_3 coordinate system. The set is the basis for the analysis and is used here to illustrate the development of inhomogeneous, two-dimensional shear using Eq. (3). Initially, by setting all F and f terms to zero in Eq. (3) except $F_{13}^{(0)} > 0$ the transformation gives rise to the familiar deformed state of homogeneous, one-dimensional, horizontal simple shear. The deformed square is shown as the solid line parallelogram in the diagram of Figure 4(a). The positive shear angle γ between the undeformed dashed vertical lines and the deformed solid diagonal lines is given by $\gamma = \tan^{-1}(F_{13}^{(0)})$. The shear deformation value γ has the familiar interpretation of the change in angle between two initially perpendicular lines. Here $\gamma = 20^\circ$. Figure 4(b) shows an analogous

diagram for $F_{13}^{(0)} < 0$, in which the shear angle is now negative, $\gamma = -20^\circ$. Further analogies are those in which all F and f terms are zero in Eq. (3) except $F_{31}^{(0)} > 0$ and $F_{31}^{(0)} < 0$, giving rise to homogeneous positive and negative vertical simple shears, shown in the diagrams of Figs. 4(c) and 4(d), respectively, using $|\gamma| = 20^\circ$. The deformed states of Figs. 4(a), 4(b), 4(c), and 4(d) are all congruent under rotation and reflection operations. The deformed states are also homogeneous, as the F_{ij}^0 terms are invariant (simply, γ is the same throughout the deformed body as F_{ij}^0 does not depend on X_1 or X_3). The simple shear deformations shown in the first column of Fig. 4, (a) through (d), may be superposed to generate other modes of deformation. For example: superposition of horizontal and vertical simple shear states of the same sign, e.g., Figs. 4(a) and 4(c), generates a state of pure shear, illustrated in the second column of Fig. 4; superposition of horizontal and vertical simple shear states of opposite sign, e.g., Figs. 4(a) and 4(d), approximates rotation, also illustrated in the second column of Fig. 4. In both cases, as the constituent deformation states were homogeneous, the resulting superposed deformation states are also homogeneous.

Figure 4. Diagrams representing homogeneous deformation. Left: one-dimensional simple shear (a) positive horizontal, (b) negative horizontal, (c) positive vertical, and (d) negative vertical. Right: two dimensional deformation formed by combinations of simple shears (a) + (c) pure shear and (a) + (d) rotation and minor dilatation.

As in Fig. 4, Fig. 5 shows a set of undeformed unit squares as dashed lines. Setting all F and f terms to zero except $f_{13}^{(1)} > 0$ in Eq. (3) gives rise to a deformed state of *inhomogeneous* horizontal one-dimensional shear. The resulting deformed square is shown as the solid line quadrilateral in Fig. 5(a). The horizontal shear angle now *increases* from $\gamma = 0$ at $X_1 = 0$ to a maximum value of $\gamma_{\max} = \tan^{-1}(f_{13}^{(1)})$ at $X_1 = 1$, giving rise to the asymmetric deformed final state. Here $\gamma_{\max} = 20^\circ$. Figure 5(b) shows an analogous diagram for $f_{13}^{(1)} < 0$, in which the shear angle decreases from 0 to a minimum negative value $-\gamma_{\max}$ at $X_1 = 1$, giving rise to a differently-shaped asymmetric final state. The further analogies, in which all F and f terms are zero except $f_{31}^{(3)} > 0$ and $f_{31}^{(3)} < 0$, give rise to inhomogeneous vertical positive and negative shears, shown in the diagrams of Figs. 5(c) and 5(d), respectively.

Figure 5. Diagrams representing inhomogeneous non-affine deformation. Left: one-dimensional graded shear (a) positive horizontal, (b) negative horizontal, (c) positive vertical, and (d) negative vertical. Right: two dimensional deformation formed by combinations of graded shears (a) + (c) graded tension, (b) + (d) graded compression, (b) + (c) graded negative rotation and minor shear, and (a) + (d) graded positive rotation and minor shear.

Figures 5(a) through 5(d), illustrating inhomogeneous shear, are analogous to Figs. 4(a) through 4(d) illustrating homogeneous shear. However, the inhomogeneous deformation leads to congruency on rotation and reflection in the inhomogeneously states only between Figs. 5(a) and 5(c) and between Figs. 5(b) and 5(d). The inhomogeneous one-dimensional horizontal and vertical shears of the first column of Fig. 5, (a) through (d), may be superposed to generate inhomogeneous *two-dimensional* modes of deformation. For example, the upper diagrams in the second column of Fig. 5 show the superposition of inhomogeneous horizontal and vertical shears of the same sign, positive or negative, leading to symmetric kite shapes. To first approximation, the resulting states are uniaxial inhomogeneous deformation, tensile or compressive, respectively, oriented at $\pi/4$ to \mathbf{e}_1 and \mathbf{e}_3 along $[10\bar{1}]$. Of most interest here, however, are the lower diagrams in the second column of Fig. 5 that show the superposition of inhomogeneous horizontal and vertical shears of opposite sign. The resulting deformed quadrilateral outlines are only approximately kite shaped with major axes located on the $[10\bar{1}]$ diagonals of the undeformed squares. The resulting inhomogeneous deformations lead to congruency on rotation and reflection here only between these two lower diagrams, 5(b) + (c) and 5(a) + (d). Figure 5(a) + (d) represents the basis for the BaTiO₃ domain boundary model to be developed. The required analysis is continued in the following section by consideration of the specific, constrained, shears required to obtain the c^+/a^+ boundary cell.

2.3. Constrained Shear Deformation

The continuous transformations described by Eq. (3) require modification for application to the discrete lattice forming a BaTiO₃ domain boundary cell. Modification begins by selection of an initial state as a region of $n \times n$ tetragonal unit cells with c domain orientation and rectangular dimensions of $na \times nc$. For example, the region may be considered the $4a \times 4c$ rectangle on the left of Fig. 1. The first modifications to the transformation equations are that (i) the X_i terms are scaled by na or nc as appropriate and (ii) the deformation is considered to be solely inhomogeneous within the boundary region, such that only the f terms in Eq. (3) are retained. Equation (3) thus becomes

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & f_{13}^{(1)}(X_1/na) \\ f_{31}^{(3)}(X_3/nc) & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X_1 \\ X_3 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

The f terms remain dimensionless and the scaled dimensions (X_1/na) and (X_3/nc) vary within the untransformed region in discrete steps between 0 and 1. Constraints on the values of the f terms are imposed by the required shape and symmetry of the boundary region. For the transformed region to resemble the general kite shape of Fig. 5(a) + (d), the terms $f_{13}^{(1)}$ and $f_{31}^{(3)}$

must be of opposite sign. More stringently, the final deformed state of the $na \times nc$ region for a BaTiO₃ $c//a^+$ boundary must be a *symmetric* kite shape with a (101) reflection plane and thus $[10\bar{1}]$ major diagonal (in conventional c -orientation crystallographic coordinates), Fig. 1. As a consequence, the magnitudes of the $f_{13}^{(1)}$ and $f_{31}^{(3)}$ terms in Eq. (4) are not independent, requiring a second modification to the transformation equations.

Figure 6. Diagram illustrating the parameters required to describe a $c//a$ transformation for a boundary cell separating the c and a cells. Note that the angles ψ and θ_r and the tensor components $f_{13}^{(1)}$ and $f_{31}^{(3)}$ are completely specified by the cell dimensions c and a if the major diagonal of the boundary cell (fine dashed) is constrained to be a line of reflection.

Figure 6 shows a schematic diagram of a domain boundary cell from Fig. 1, providing a basis for development of geometrical constraints on the values of $f_{13}^{(1)}$ and $f_{31}^{(3)}$. The initial c domain tetragonal unit cell is shown by the dashed line and the deformed boundary cell is shown by the solid line. The trace of a diagonal (101) plane of the initial cell is also shown dashed and the angle between this trace and e_3 is

$$\psi = \tan^{-1}(a/c). \quad (5)$$

This plane becomes a reflection symmetry plane in the deformed cell, such that the long sides of the deformed cell are both dimension c and at angle ψ to the reflection plane; the short sides of

the deformed cell are both dimension a . The angle between pairs of sides in the deformed and initial configurations is thus either 0 (bottom and left) or θ_T (top and right), where

$$\theta_T = \pi/2 - 2\psi. \quad (6)$$

Note that Eqs. (5) and (6) are simply descriptions of a symmetric kite shape for sides of a given length. Trigonometric identities can be used to combine the two equations into a single relation, eliminating ψ and expressing $\sin \theta_T$ as

$$\sin \theta_T = [1 - (a/c)^2]/[1 + (a/c)^2]. \quad (7)$$

In order to generate the specific transformation illustrated in Figs. 1 and 6, Eq. (7) provides a convenient constraint on the general transformation of Eq. (4) and enables the determination of the required relationship between the $f_{13}^{(1)}$ and $f_{31}^{(3)}$ terms.

A single transformed position expressed in two ways, generally and specifically, can be used to determine the two $f_{13}^{(1)}$ and $f_{31}^{(3)}$ terms. For an initial position of $(X_1, X_3) = (a, c)$, the general transformation of Eq. (4) gives the deformed position as

$$x_1 = a + f_{13}^{(1)}c, \quad (8a)$$

$$x_3 = c + f_{31}^{(3)}a. \quad (8b)$$

For the same initial position, the specific constraint of the reflection symmetry illustrated in Fig. 6 gives the deformed position as

$$x_1 = a + a \sin \theta_T, \quad (9a)$$

$$x_3 = c - c \sin \theta_T. \quad (9b)$$

On elimination of x_1 between Eqs. (8a) and (9a), x_3 between Eqs. (8b) and (9b), and $\sin \theta_T$ using Eq. (7), the expressions for $f_{13}^{(1)}$ and $f_{31}^{(3)}$ are

$$f_{13}^{(1)} = (a/c)[1 - (a/c)^2]/[1 + (a/c)^2], \quad (10a)$$

$$f_{31}^{(3)} = - (c/a)[1 - (a/c)^2]/[1 + (a/c)^2]. \quad (10b)$$

The ratio of these two expressions is

$$f_{31}^{(3)}/f_{13}^{(1)} = -c^2/a^2, \quad (11)$$

showing that the inhomogeneous shear amplitude terms are indeed related only by the tetragonal distortion and are of different magnitude and sign. [Equation (9) can also be written as $x_1 = c \cos \theta_T$ and $x_3 = a \cos \theta_T$, showing that the ratios of the initial and transformed coordinates are reciprocally related by $X_3/X_1 = c/a$ and $x_3/x_1 = a/c$.] For BaTiO₃, $c/a = 1.01$, and thus $f_{13}^{(1)} \simeq 0.0108$, $f_{31}^{(3)} \simeq -0.0111$, and $\sin \theta_T = 0.0109$. For the examples here, $c/a = 1.2$ or $c/a = 1.3$. For $c/a = 1.2$, $f_{13}^{(1)} \simeq 0.15$, $f_{31}^{(3)} \simeq -0.22$, and $\sin \theta_T = 0.1803$.

Setting $\sin \theta_T = q$ for convenience gives the general deformation equations within the $na \times nc$ region as

$$x_1 = X_1 + (qna)(X_1/na)(X_3/nc), \quad (12a)$$

$$x_3 = X_3 - (qnc)(X_3/nc)(X_1/na). \quad (12b)$$

Using these equations shows that the major diagonal $[10\bar{1}]$ remains an invariant straight line on deformation. The equation of this initial major diagonal is

$$(X_3/nc) = 1 - (X_1/na). \quad (13)$$

Replacing initial coordinates with transformed coordinates using Eq. (12) in Eq. (13) gives the identical transformed major diagonal equation:

$$(x_3/nc) = 1 - (x_1/na). \quad (14)$$

The minor diagonal, $[101]$ in the undeformed state becomes, on deformation, a quadratic curve that depends on the undeformed position. The equation of this initial straight-line minor diagonal is

$$(X_3/nc) = (X_1/na) \quad (15)$$

Replacing initial coordinates with transformed coordinates using Eq. (12) in Eq. (15) gives the transformed minor diagonal as a parametric curved equation in the initial coordinate (X_1/na) :

$$(x_3/nc) = (x_1/na) - 2q(X_1/na)^2, \quad (16)$$

which is not a straight line. For comparison, the straight line minor diagonal of the deformed state is given by

$$(x_3/nc) = (x_1/na)(1 - q)/(1 + q), \quad (17)$$

which is the asymptote of Eq. (16) as $x_1 \rightarrow 0$.

2.4. Strain and Rotation

The material displacement gradient tensor is given by $J_{ij} = F_{ij} - \delta_{ij}$ [Mase, 1970] (in EBSD applications often termed the distortion tensor, a_{ij} or A_{ij} [Howell, 2014, 2017, 2019, 2020]).

Using Eqs. (4) and (10) thus gives

$$J_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & (qa/c)(X_1/na) \\ -(qc/a)(X_3/nc) & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (18)$$

Separating J_{ij} into symmetric, l_{ij} , and antisymmetric, W_{ij} , components, gives the infinitesimal

Lagrangian strain tensor,

$$l_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & (q/2)[(a/c)(X_1/na) - (c/a)(X_3/nc)] \\ (q/2)[(a/c)(X_1/na) - (c/a)(X_3/nc)] & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (19)$$

and the infinitesimal Lagrangian rotation tensor,

$$W_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & (q/2)[(a/c)(X_1/na) + (c/a)(X_3/nc)] \\ -(q/2)[(a/c)(X_1/na) + (c/a)(X_3/nc)] & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (20)$$

For all c/a ratios, Eq. (19) shows that the strain tensor consists of a single shear strain component, $l_{13} = l_{31}$. The component is zero along a straight line very close to the undeformed minor diagonal, given by

$$(X_3/nc) = a^2/c^2(X_1/na). \quad (21)$$

For $c > a$, negative shear strains lie above this line, positive shear strains lie below this line, and the average shear strain within the region is negative. Other contours of strain are parallel to this line. For BaTiO₃, $c \simeq a$, and hence to the lowest order of approximation there is zero average shear strain within the region and the deformation is thus all rotation. For all c/a ratios, Eq. (20) shows that the rotation tensor consists of single independent component, $W_{13} = -W_{31}$, that leads to the rotation vector component $w_2 = (W_{13} - W_{31})/2$ [Mase, 1970]. The component is zero at $X_1 = X_3 = 0$ and away from this point describes increasingly positive rotation about \mathbf{e}_2 throughout the region. In the undeformed state the contours of rotation are parallel to the major diagonal. The variation of deformation throughout the deformed region is obtained by treating X_1 and X_3 as parameters connecting the deformed coordinates, x_1 and x_3 , Eq. (12), to the strain l_{ij} and rotation W_{ij} , Eqs. (19) and (20). This procedure is simply performed numerically.

2.5. Polarization

The electric dipole moment of a BaTiO₃ unit cell is determined by the position of the interior Ti⁴⁺ ion relative to the positions of the Ba²⁺ and O²⁻ ions located on the vertices and faces of the cell exterior [Kwei *et al.*, 1993; Jona and Shirane, 1993]. At temperatures greater than 140 °C, the cell exterior is cubic, the Ti⁴⁺ ion is located at the center of the cell, and the cell exhibits zero dipole moment. At temperatures less than 140 °C, the cell exterior is tetragonal, formed by a longer c dimension relative to the two shorter a dimensions. The Ti⁴⁺ ion increases the cell tetragonal symmetry by interior displacement, parallel to the c axis within the cell, to one of two equivalent positions away from the cell center. The displacement generates an electric dipole oriented parallel to the c axis in one of two directions, characterized as + and – relative to a fixed coordinate system. For example, the dipoles in Fig. 2 are all locally aligned parallel to the long axes of the tetragonal unit cells. Relative to the fixed \mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{e}_2 - \mathbf{e}_3 frame the tetragonal cells are designated as c^+ and a^+ in Fig. 2(a), c^- and a^- in Fig. 2(b), c^+ and a^- in Fig. 2(c), and so on.

In the context of the above deformation, the c^+ and a^+ cells in Figs. 1, 2, and implicit in Fig. 6 are related by rotation and translation operations such that

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}_{a^+} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\pi/2 + \theta_r) & -\sin(\pi/2 + \theta_r) \\ \sin(\pi/2 + \theta_r) & \cos(\pi/2 + \theta_r) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X_1 \\ X_3 \end{bmatrix}_{c^+} + \mathbf{t}, \quad (22)$$

where the matrix is recognized as rotating the cell coordinates by $\pi/2 + \theta_r$ and \mathbf{t} is a translation vector. The polarization state, \mathbf{p}_{c^+} , of the initial c^+ cells in \mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{e}_3 coordinates is

$$\mathbf{p}_{c^+} = p_0 \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (23)$$

where p_0 is the polarization magnitude of BaTiO₃ in the tetragonal state. The polarization state of the a^+ cells is thus given simply by the same $\pi/2 + \theta_r$ rotation:

$$\mathbf{p}_{a^+} = p_0 \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\pi/2 + \theta_r) & -\sin(\pi/2 + \theta_r) \\ \sin(\pi/2 + \theta_r) & \cos(\pi/2 + \theta_r) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (23b)$$

The polarization of the domain boundary cells, \mathbf{p}_{db} , is determined by the local deformation field—strain and rotation—within the boundary region, and given by:

$$\mathbf{p}_{db} = p_b \begin{bmatrix} \cos\theta_b & -\sin\theta_b \\ \sin\theta_b & \cos\theta_b \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (24)$$

where $p_b = p_b(X_1, X_3)$ and $\theta_b = \theta_b(X_1, X_3)$ are location-dependent functions that match the bounding conditions of Eq. (23) describing polarization magnitude and orientation, respectively. For consistency with Eqs. (19) and (20), the functions are taken here as linear:

$$p_b = p_{\min} + [p_0 - p_{\min}] |(X_1/na) + (X_3/nc) - 1|, \quad (25a)$$

where p_{\min} is a characteristic minimum polarization within the domain boundary region, and

$$\theta_b = [\pi/2 + \theta_r][(X_1/na) + (X_3/nc)]/2. \quad (25b)$$

Equation (25) describes the physical observation [Howell, 2014, 2017, 2019, 2020] that BaTiO₃ unit cells become “more cubic” within domain boundary regions and thus become less electrically polarized, as well as rotated. Equation (25) also matches the obvious bounding conditions. Along the major diagonal of the boundary region, inserting Eq. (13) into Eq. (25a), the polarization magnitude is at the minimum value, $p_b = p_{\min}$. Away from this line, the polarization increases, such that at the limits of the minor diagonal, the “corners” of the boundary region, the polarization magnitude is at the maximum value, $p_b = p_0$, obtained by inserting Eq. (15) into Eq. (25a). Equation (25b) shows that the polarization rotation is zero, $\theta_b = 0$, at $X_1 = X_3 = 0$, and away from this point describes increasingly positive rotation throughout the region, reaching maximum rotation, $\theta_b = (\pi/2 + \theta_r)$, at $(X_1/na) = (X_3/nc) = 1$. Along the major diagonal of the boundary region, inserting Eq. (13) into Eq. (25b), the polarization orientation is the average value, $\theta_b = (\pi/2 + \theta_r)/2$.

3. Results

Figure 7 shows a domain boundary as part of a $c//a$ structure, generalizing Fig. 1 to include an extended boundary region of variable strain and rotation that gradually changes the exterior

structure of the cells from c domain to a domain. Relative to the c domain, structure in the boundary region is given by Eqs. (4) and (10) and in the a domain by Eq. (22). The boundary region is clearly symmetric about the invariant major diagonal and includes a smooth transition from cells similar to the c domain at the lower left of the region to cells similar to the a domain at the upper right of the region at the limits of the minor diagonal. The cells at the center of the region are approximately square.

Figure 7. Diagram of an extended domain boundary region (red in color) separating domains of different orientation (blue and green in color). The boundary region is formed by inhomogeneous strain and rotation of the domains either side, as described by the analysis here. The number of cells, $n = 7$, the aspect ratio of the undeformed cells is $c/a = 1.3$, and the units of the graph are cell a dimension. Compare with Fig. 1.

In more detail, Figs. 8 and 9, show color-filled contour maps of the strain and rotation within the boundary region. Figure 8 shows contours of the l_{13} shear strain component in undeformed coordinates. The transition in shear strain from negative to positive across a line of zero strain slightly removed from the minor diagonal is clear. Figure 9(a) shows the same l_{13} shear strain contours in deformed coordinates. The interior deformation of the boundary region is made clear by the obvious curvature, described by Eq. (16), of the originally straight minor diagonal and related strain contours. In contrast, Fig. 9(b) shows straight-line contours of the W_{13} rotation component in deformed coordinates. Rotation increases linearly from zero in the lower left of the boundary region to a positive value in the upper right of the region, although not directly along the minor diagonal of the deformed region.

Figure 8. Color filled contour map in initial, undeformed coordinates of the shear strain component l_{13} within a domain boundary region. The transition from negative to positive shear strain from top to bottom of the region and the line of zero shear strain are clear. The ratio $c/a = 1.2$.

Figure 9. Color filled contour maps in deformed coordinates of the (a) shear strain l_{13} and (b) rotation W_{13} within the domain boundary region of Fig. 8. The transition from negative to positive shear strain from top to bottom and increasing rotation from bottom to top are clear.

Figure 10 shows the domain boundary region from Fig. 7 with superimposed electric polarization vectors within the cells. The vectors were calculated using Eqs. (24) and (25). The major polarization features discussed above are clear: minimum polarization along the major diagonal symmetry line increasing to maximum polarization in the boundary region corners at the limits of the minor diagonal; gradual rotation of the polarization between these corners to align with the left c domain and right a domain; fixed, intermediate polarization orientation along the major diagonal.

Figure 10. Diagram of extended domain boundary region from Fig. 7 including electric polarization vectors. The rotation of the vectors from left to right is clear. The magnitude of the vectors increases from minima of $p_{\min} = 0.3p_0$ at the center of the region to maxima of $\approx p_0$ at the edges of the region.

A final result here is the surface structure of an a domain in a c domain matrix, the $c^+//a^+//c^+$ structure, shown in Fig. 11. Such a structure is typical of BaTiO_3 microstructures consisting of lamellar [Howell, 2014, 2019] or bundled [Howell, 2017, 2019] domains. The structure is an example application of the analysis above and highlights two additional points. First, the extended domain boundary regions do not remove surface roughness, but simply accommodate over longer distances the surface height and surface gradient discontinuities associated with different domains. Comparison of Fig. 1 and Fig. 11 illustrates the surface

smoothing effect of the extended boundary regions and the likely effects of depth weighted strain and rotation measurements. Second, the simple form of Eq. 25 leads to polarization discontinuities at displacement gradient discontinuities, here at the top left and bottom right of the boundary regions. A polarization scheme that maintained symmetry *across* the major diagonal (as here) but not necessarily *along* the major diagonal (taking domain proximity into account) would provide a mechanism for discontinuity removal.

Figure 11. Diagram of the BaTiO₃ $c^+//a^+//c^+$ microstructure including extended domain boundary regions with inhomogeneous strain, rotation, and polarization leading to gradual mechanical and electrical variation between domains. The number of cells is $n = 5$, the aspect ratio of the cells is $c/a = 1.2$, and the minimum electrical polarization is $p_{\min} = 0.5p_0$.

4. Summary

A kinematic model, based on non-affine shear deformation, was developed to describe 90° domain boundary structures in BaTiO₃. The model boundary structures were spatially extended, consistent with experimental observations of strain and rotation variation at domain boundaries and with dynamics based models. The kinematic model was based on a simple continuum mechanics deformation analysis and included as a limiting case an often cited schematic diagram of a 90° domain boundary in BaTiO₃. The model is easily considered in initial and deformed coordinates and provides explicit predictions for the spatial variations in strain and rotation throughout the domain boundary region for direct comparison with experimental deformation measurement techniques such as EBSD. Polarization of the BaTiO₃ cells within the domain boundary region were mapped onto the deformation in a simple scheme consistent with the symmetry of the region. An example structure consisting of two boundary regions separating

three domains was demonstrated; more extensive and complicated structures are easily constructed using rigid body symmetry operations of translation, rotation, and reflection.

Appendix: Deformation Curvature

If all terms in Eq. (1) are retained, the displacement field u_i in an \mathbf{e}_1 - \mathbf{e}_2 frame obtained on integration is

$$u_1 = x_1 - X_1 = F_{12}^0 X_2 + f_{12}^{(1)} X_1 X_2 + f_{12}^{(2)} X_2^2 \quad (\text{A1})$$

$$u_2 = x_2 - X_2 = F_{21}^0 X_1 + f_{21}^{(2)} X_1 X_2 + f_{21}^{(1)} X_1^2. \quad (\text{A2})$$

The displacements include quadratic terms X_1^2 and X_2^2 leading to deformation curvature, $\partial^2 u_i / \partial X_j^2 \neq 0$. Examples are shown in Fig. A1.

Figure A1. Deformation curvature generated by non-affine quadratic deformation terms. (a) “wave”, $f_{12}^{(2)} > 0$, (b) “curl”, $f_{21}^{(1)} > 0$, (c) arrowhead”, $f_{12}^{(2)} > 0$ and $f_{21}^{(1)} > 0$, (d) “handkerchief”, all terms $\neq 0$.

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